

DECOMPOSER: Functional decomposition and distributed execution of monolithic applications to heterogeneous resources

Guilherme Mendes Vieira de Matos
Andrew Williams
 Federal University of São Carlos, Brazil
 Ericsson Research, Sweden

Abstract—In current computing processing infrastructures, optimizing performance and energy efficiency across heterogeneous hardware environments remains a critical challenge. Recently, the growth of different types of hardware architectures has raised challenges but also opportunities. In this paper, we present Decomposer, designed to decompose monolithic applications into modular components, allowing them to be executed across various combinations of hardware architectures, both locally and in distributed settings. Using static and dynamic analysis, Decomposer allows flexible allocation of functions to different targets, optimizing both execution time and energy consumption. Our approach involves the generation of Intermediate Representations (IR) using LLVM and MLIR, allowing the identification of functions for decomposition and their distributed execution on heterogeneous hardware. By expanding execution options, Decomposer provides flexibility in resource allocation without increasing execution times. Furthermore, we observed that such decomposition improves cache utilization, reducing L1 cache misses and L2 references in more than 50%, thus enhancing memory efficiency. This work, although in its initial phase, shows that this approach allows for dynamic workload distribution across multiple targets, offering a more versatile and adaptable solution for application execution, aligning resource usage with operational objectives and environmental considerations. We envisage that the compilers area and its techniques can be very useful for optimizing a set of applications to be decomposed and run not only in core data centers but also at the edge 5G network.

Index Terms—Edge computing, heterogeneous environment, application decomposition, disaggregation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The limitations of CPU advancements due to the slowdown of Dennard scaling and Moore’s Law have created a gap between general-purpose processor progress and the rapid growth of data, which doubles every two years [1]. This imbalance is evident with the increasing use of high-bandwidth I/O devices, such as SSDs and NICs, which have significantly accelerated data movement. However, since CPU instructions per byte access during I/O remain constant [2], this higher data rate consumes more CPU resources [3]. As a response, accelerators like GPUs, FPGAs, DPUs, and TPUs are being widely adopted in modern IT computing infrastructures [4]. Network resources have also evolved, with programmable

control and data planes [5], [6], leading to the deployment of switches and SmartNICs in the core cloud (eg. data centers) as well as in the edge [7].

The shift towards heterogeneous environments necessitates offloading, where intensive tasks are shifted to specialized devices like GPUs or SmartNICs, enhancing efficiency. This highlights the importance of modular architectures that can dynamically allocate tasks to the most appropriate hardware.

In response, disaggregation has emerged, organizing resources like memory, processing, and networking into independent pools, improving scalability and resource management. This environment presents new challenges, requiring careful analysis of both the application and available hardware to choose the best execution strategy. Traditionally, IT computing infrastructures rely on a single processor architecture, but now we can leverage multiple types to optimize performance and energy use.

Edge computing adds another dimension, offering diverse hardware resources across distributed locations. Applications can be decomposed into smaller functions that execute on the most suitable hardware, balancing factors like performance, low latency, and energy efficiency. Functional decomposition is key here, allowing dynamic distribution of tasks based on hardware capabilities, whether in data centers or at the edge.

This paper presents Decomposer, a solution to optimize workloads in disaggregated IT computing infrastructures through functional decomposition. Decomposer breaks monolithic applications into smaller, independent functions that can be assigned to the most appropriate hardware based on the application needs and available resources. This process involves static analysis of the application, using intermediate representation (IR) to identify function boundaries, extracting these functions, and compiling them for different hardware targets. Once decomposed, we perform a dynamic analysis, where each function is executed on a dedicated core and on multiple servers, where execution information is collected, such as time, energy consumption, and performance in relation to memory utilization. All these results are compiled in order to create a range of opportunities, where it is possible to verify several different combinations to run what was previously a

monolithic application, that is, would be executed on a single server.

In this paper, we focus on running convolution neural networks which is a typical block commonly used in image and video analysis for detection, recognition, reconstruction, and object tracking of Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR), Mixed Reality (MR), and Extended Reality (XR).

Our results demonstrate that this approach not only improves cache utilization in more than 50% while maintaining execution time, but also allows dynamic adaptability across different hardware architectures, further emphasizing its potential to optimize performance in diverse environments. By creating the possibility of executing a previously monolithic application in a decomposed manner, Desomposer ensures better resource allocation and bottleneck reduction. By adapting (through decomposition) the application to the execution environment considering the specific requirements of each function, this method optimizes performance and energy efficiency while maintaining communication between distributed components.

II. FUNDAMENTAL CONCEPTS

The Von Neumann architecture, proposed by John von Neumann in 1945, describes a computer model where the CPU executes instructions stored in memory and uses a common bus to access both instructions and data [8]. This architecture has shaped the server-centric era, where all resources such as memory, processor and storage are centralized in a single machine that generally has a single operating system orchestrating these resources [9], as we can see in Figure 1-A. However, the Von Neumann architecture does not specify that the computing resources must necessarily be physically in the same enclosure. The core concept is that the CPU and memory are logically connected and share a common bus for communication. In the modern context, this still holds true, but the physical distribution of the components may vary, especially in more complex architectures such as distributed systems or disaggregated datacenters, as we will discuss below.

A. Disaggregated environment

As illustrated in Figure 1-C, the disaggregated environment is defined as one where computing resources are not centralized, but rather organized into self-managed pools, connected via network [1]. A good example of a resource that has already been disaggregated is storage [10]. Much work has been done involving the creation of other physical hardwares [11], [12], runtimes [13]–[15], operating systems [9], network disaggregation [16] and many others, culminating in a complete end-to-end disaggregated system [17].

After a deep research, we realize that these works involve only basic computing resources, such as memory, CPUs, storage and network. However, we are aware that currently there are many specialized resources, or accelerators, such as FPGA, GPU, TPU, DPU, among others being used to try to compensate for the imbalance caused by Dennard and Moore’s laws slow down. It is expected that in a disaggregated

environment, there will be not only pools of basic resources but also specialized ones. Furthermore, we observe a trend that we term homogeneous disaggregation, where current disaggregation implementations focus on like resources, such as CPU or memory pools of the same type (e.g., all Intel CPUs or all AMD CPUs). However, the real challenge lies in managing a heterogeneous disaggregated environment, where we have pools of various general-purpose processors (e.g., Intel, AMD), memories, and accelerators. This demands sophisticated workload distribution, interoperability across architectures, and efficient software that can manage resource heterogeneity effectively.

This work aims to explore the feasibility of heterogeneous disaggregated environments and the challenges they present.

B. Heterogeneous environment

Specialized resources or accelerators are often referred to as heterogeneous resources because they differ significantly from traditional CPUs in terms of architecture, purpose, and performance [18]. As depicted in figure 1-B, these accelerators are commonly deployed in server-centric environments to boost applications performance by offloading specific workloads from CPUs. This introduces a heterogeneous environment, where, although the architecture remains server-centric, there is the added complexity of allocating specific tasks to the most suitable hardware, such as GPUs, FPGAs, or other accelerators. Much work has been done to deal with this environment, involving identifying offloading opportunities and allocating them to accelerators. [19]–[26]. [27], [28].

In traditional server-centric environments, heterogeneity typically arises from the addition of accelerators to a single type of general-purpose processor (often Intel or AMD). However, this limitation could be overcome in disaggregated environments, where heterogeneous resources (ranging from multiple types of CPUs to various accelerators) could be dynamically allocated based on workload characteristics. The edge computing landscape already presents examples of this, where servers feature diverse processors and each may have different accelerators, complicating the challenge of determining the optimal target for a given task.

C. Offloading vs disaggregation vs decomposition

It is important to distinguish between offloading, disaggregation, and functional decomposition, as each addresses different challenges in heterogeneous and disaggregated environments.

Offloading is a practice commonly used in heterogeneous systems, where specific, compute-intensive parts of the code are delegated to specialized accelerators like GPUs or FPGAs to improve performance. The focus is on utilizing these specialized components to handle particular tasks, requiring the use of specific APIs like CUDA [29] or OpenCL [30], along with careful memory management and synchronization. The key goal in offloading is to improve efficiency within the boundaries of a single server by utilizing accelerators that are part of that server.

Fig. 1: Architecture models.

Disaggregation, on the other hand, abstracts the physical location of resources, enabling distributed components—such as CPUs, memory, and storage—to be accessed as if they were part of a single logical system. This paradigm allows for greater flexibility in resource allocation, as components no longer need to be physically co-located. Technologies like Compute Express Link (CXL) [31] and RDMA over Converged Ethernet (RoCE) [32] are critical to this approach, providing low-latency, high-bandwidth communication between disaggregated elements. In a disaggregated setup, for instance, the memory used by a process might reside on one server, while the CPU executing the code is on another. The key benefit here is the transparent allocation of resources across a network, unbounded by the physical constraints of a single machine.

Functional decomposition, the approach we propose, complements both offloading and disaggregation but operates on a broader scale. It involves breaking a monolithic application into smaller, self-contained functional blocks. Each block can then be dynamically assigned to the most suitable resource, whether in a heterogeneous (offloading) or disaggregated environment. Unlike offloading, which focuses on specific tasks within a server, functional decomposition enables fine-grained control over the execution of the entire application. This allows for optimal allocation not only within a single server but across distributed, disaggregated systems, leveraging the most appropriate hardware—be it a GPU, FPGA, or remote CPU—based on performance, energy efficiency, or resource availability.

In this way, functional decomposition serves both heterogeneous and disaggregated environments by ensuring that tasks are executed on the best available hardware. This dynamic allocation results in increased flexibility, better resource utilization, and improved performance, catering to the growing complexity of modern data center and edge computing environments.

III. DECOMPOSER WORKFLOW

This section starts by acknowledging that existing approaches enable the execution of monolithic applications in disaggregated homogeneous environments [33], but these solutions generally do not consider heterogeneous resources. Our work expands this scope by focusing on distributing native ap-

plications across heterogeneous resources within disaggregated and also heterogeneous environments, accounting for the interplay between different types of processors and computational units. Specifically, our goal is to decompose an application into multiple functional blocks, allowing each functional block to be executed on a different target. This will enable various scenarios regarding time and energy consumption, bringing flexibility, better resource utilization, and improved alignment with the SLAs and KPIs of each application, both in heterogeneous and disaggregated environments.

One possible strategy could be to target applications designed with heterogeneity in mind, using APIs such as CUDA [29] or OpenCL [30]. However, heterogeneity in our context goes beyond traditional GPU-CPU interactions; it involves the coexistence of CPUs with different architectures, FPGAs, GPUs and others within the same environment. Therefore, identifying the optimal hardware target requires analyzing the application as a whole, focusing on performance and energy efficiency.

To achieve the goal we proposed, we defined a workflow depicted in Figure 2. This workflow is divided into two strategies, static (green blocks) and dynamic (blue blocks) analyzes. We begin with static analyses generating intermediate representations (IRs) of the target application (as will be seen in more detail in Section III-A), where we collect information about the application and also prepare it for dynamic analysis (Section III-B), where we can identify hotspots, energy consumption, and execution time across multiple hardware platforms. Based on the results of the analysis, we have both, the decomposed application and information about the characteristics of each decomposed application on top of each target, such as energy consumption, execution time, and cache memory performance. The following sections will delve into the tools and techniques employed.

A. Static analysis

We begin our static analysis considering that our intention is to decompose a monolithic application into several functional blocks, so we first need to understand the pipeline of this application regarding its memory and processing operations, functions and flow. There are several articles that mention the use of LLVM [34] and MLIR [35] as tools that can create intermediate representations (IR), which are representations of

Fig. 2: Decomposer workflow.

the application in a language that allows not only the reading and understanding of the application, but also the performance assessment of several operations. Among these operations, in the context of our work, the possibility of listing and extracting functions, and also the possibility of joint compilation of representations, stand out.

Fig. 3: Callgraph.

Using LLVM, an IR is created from a monolithic application. On top of this first version, analysis are performed to discover which functions exist in the application and extract them, creating new IRs, one for each function existing in the original application. Each new representation extracted will become a decomposed application. Figure 3 is a graphic representation of a callgraph, one of the several options that LLVM is capable of generating as output. With a callgraph, it is possible to determine the order in which the functions are called, that is, it determines the order in which each new application will be executed. We also take into account data dependency for functional decomposition, that is, when and what data should be sent to each decomposed application. This is important to maintain data consistency and prevent data from skipping processing steps, causing the decomposed application to crash. To determine data dependency, MLIR is used to create a second IR, this one with a different pattern from the one created by LLVM. While the IR created by LLVM can be directly compared with the application binary, representing the application pipeline in terms of machine instructions, the IR created by MLIR allows a more clear visualization of both, the declared data and its use within each function. By doing this, the functions, the data, the

order of execution of the functions and the data dependency of each function are extracted and jointly considered for the decomposition and creation of each decomposed application.

Finally, it is necessary to transform each new IR created into an application. Both LLVM and MLIR allow compiling IRs for various targets. As this is an initial work where we want to test the concept and verify its efficiency, we are initially taking into account only general-purpose processors, therefore, we use LLVM to compile the applications, as this tool has proven to be more user-friendly. However, we intend to use MLIR and extend the hardware range, allowing the decomposition of applications using GPUs and FPGAs as well. The Decomposer was created based on the premise that the system knows the environment and is aware of the targets and their respective network addresses. Furthermore, compiling a function alone is insufficient for proper execution or inter-function communication. Therefore, we develop an algorithm that creates a decomposed application for each hardware, compiles each extracted IR with a generic driver (Section III-C), and can be changed at runtime to represent a specific hardware, having as input the target architecture and network address.

The total number of applications generated will be the result of S^A , where A is the number of functions to be decomposed and S is the number of targets available in the environment. For example, if the result of our static analysis indicates that we have 3 functions to be decomposed and we have 3 possible targets in our execution environment, we will then have 27 different decomposed applications, that is, one version of each decomposed application for each hardware.

B. Dynamic analysis

Both environments we work with are highly heterogeneous, featuring different general-purpose processors and GPUs from various vendors, as well as other specialized hardware. In such an environment, identifying an effective strategy for functional decomposition is particularly challenging. Our primary goal is to verify whether a monolithic application, originally designed to run on a single processor, can be decomposed for execution across multiple, heterogeneous processors.

In order to achieve this, we must first make sure to maintain the application's performance and also save energy. We decided to perform a dynamic analysis in which each application

goes through a profiling process, where data such as program execution time, execution time per function, energy consumption, and some other data are identified. These analyses are performed for each processor available in the environment. After the analysis has been performed, a list with the execution times and energy consumption for each function and hardware is obtained.

To implement this, we developed a method that receives as input the output of the static analysis, that is, the decomposed applications already compiled, one for each available target. Then the Decomposer sends the applications to the hardware and executes them, taking into account all possible combinations. The Decomposer captures information such as execution time, energy consumption and L1 and L2 cache memory performance, using the profiling tools `gprof` [36] and `perf` [37]. The results of each combination are sent to the Decomposer and recorded in a table for future analysis.

C. Communication deployment

Once we have identified all the possible disaggregation strategies, the next step is to establish communication between the functional blocks. To this end, we created a generic program that implements a main function that will be prepared to receive the memory data that each function will need, calls the extracted function and enables communication via network sockets. This driver is adaptable, meaning it can be customized for each extracted function. By analyzing the IR, we determine the function name and the memory inputs required for correct execution. Additionally, we collect communication data from the target architecture, such as IP address and port, to configure the network sockets. After this configuration, the generic driver is compiled with the extracted function to facilitate communication, allowing the different parts of the application to exchange memory data and execution results over the network. This solution effectively enables the functional decomposition of a monolithic application to run across multiple resources, while maintaining inter-block communication.

The generic driver in the DECOMPOSER workflow is designed to receive the function code for disaggregation and necessary data for node communication. While current implementations use IP and port due to socket communication, future protocols like `RoCE` and `CXL` may alter required metadata.

Much of the DECOMPOSER workflow is already automated, including the generation of intermediate representations (IR), function extraction, and linkage processes. The remaining steps required for full automation primarily involve deploying a runtime system capable of orchestrating the decomposition dynamically at application launch. This runtime will handle metadata collection, function placement decisions, and execution coordination, ensuring that the decomposition process is fully automated without requiring manual intervention.

IV. DEPLOYMENT AND EVALUATION

This section details the setup and the experiments conducted to evaluate both the monolithic and decomposed versions of

the application. We focus on testing different deployment strategies to evaluate performance, communication overhead, and potential improvements for distributed computing scenarios.

A. Setup

Fig. 4: Setup used for the evaluations.

The experimental setup is depicted in Figure 4, and consists of two geographically distributed sites, each with multiple servers of different CPU architectures and memory configurations.

- **Site 1:**

- Host1: A high-performance server with an AMD Ryzen 9 3900X (12-core, 24 threads) and 16 GB of memory.
- Host2: An Intel Xeon Silver 4208 CPU (8-core, 16 threads) with 16 GB of memory.
- Host3: A Bluefield SmartNIC equipped with an 8-core ARM Cortex-A72 processor and 16 GB of memory (attached on host1).

- **Site 2:**

- Host4: An Intel Xeon D-1518 (4-core, 8 threads) with 8 GB of memory.
- Host5: Another Intel Xeon D-1518 (4-core, 8 threads), also with 8 GB of memory.

The two sites are connected over the Internet with a distance of 1400 kilometers between them and with an average latency of 29 milliseconds. Only Host 1 from Site 1 is able to communicate with any of the servers at Site 2, making up a wide-area network scenario.

- 1) *Application structure and functional decomposition:*

The application under test is a C language simplified yet computationally intensive model, typically seen in machine learning and computer vision workloads. The core of the application consists of four functions:

- **Main Function:** This function initializes two large vectors, input and weights, both containing 10,000 double numbers, which have 8 bytes size. This means that each vector is 80 KB, so that is 160 KB plus 8 KB for the bias variable, for a total of 168 KB of data that will be sent from the main function to each other function. It then calls three convolution functions (`conv1`, `conv2`, and `conv3`) sequentially, passing these vectors as well as a bias parameter to each, totaling the sending of 504 KB.

- **Convolution Functions:** Each convolution function receives 168 KB of data and performs a specified number of operations, that represent the bulk of the computation:
 - **Conv1:** Executes 100,000 convolutions
 - **Conv2:** Executes 200,000 convolutions
 - **Conv3:** Executes 400,000 convolutions

The monolithic version of the application executes these functions sequentially on a single server. To test the impact of decomposition, the application was split into functional blocks using Decomposer, where each function was isolated and distributed across different servers in our environment, while still maintaining serialized execution, that is, the main function calls conv1 and waits for its completion, then calls conv2 and waits, followed by conv3. This decomposition introduces six network operations, three for sending data to the servers where each function is executed, and three for receiving the results, since the data is transmitted over the network for processing, rather than being handled locally.

2) *Strategies:* Using Decomposer, the application has been broken into functional blocks, with the main representing the input data (e.g., VR/AR sensor data) and conv1, conv2, and conv3 corresponding to the processing functions, such as convolution operations for AI or image analysis. These components can be executed either on the same server or distributed across multiple servers. Several execution modes were tested to evaluate the impact of decomposing the application on performance across different setups:

- **Monolithic:** The entire application (including all convolution functions) runs on a single machine, as a single process.
- **Same server,** functional blocks as separate processes:
 - In this scenario, the application was decomposed into four separate processes representing the main function and the three convolution functions (conv1, conv2, conv3). All four processes ran on the same server, simulating a monolithic environment where the only difference was that the processes were executed separately but on the same physical machine.
 - Objective: To establish a baseline for comparison and to evaluate whether decomposition introduces any overhead even when all functional blocks are on the same hardware.
- **Main function remote,** convolutions local:
 - In this deployment, the main function was offloaded to one server while the convolution functions were executed on a different server. We tested both local network communication (within Site 1) and over the Internet (Site 1 to Site 2). It is important to highlight that this use case represents a scenario with VR/AR glasses sending data over the local network or the Internet to applications that will process the data (e.g. rendering).
 - **Local network:** The main function runs on the AMD server (Host1), while the convolution functions are

executed on the Intel server (Host3). Data was passed between the processes over the local network.

- **Internet:** The main function runs on the AMD server (Host1) at Site 1, and the convolution functions runs on the Intel server at Site 2 (host4). Data was transferred between the two sites via the Internet.
- Objective: Measure the impact of network latency and bandwidth when functional blocks are physically separated, representing real-world distributed computing scenarios.

B. Evaluation

We conducted a series of experiments to measure the performance of the monolithic and decomposed versions of the application. Each experiment was run 3 times, and the results presented in the graphs and table below represent the averages of the values obtained. The main performance metrics collected included the following.

- **Execution time:** The total time taken for the entire application to complete, including the time for each convolution function and any associated communication overhead.
- **Energy consumption:** Using on-board tools and remote profiling software, we tracked energy usage across both the monolithic and decomposed versions.
- **Memory performance regarding to L1 and L2 cache:** We analyzed the cache hit and miss rates to assess the efficiency of memory usage in both versions of the application (monolithic and decomposed). Special attention was given to how each version utilized the L1 and L2 caches during execution.

The results shows that Decomposer allowed for a flexible mapping of computational tasks (convolution layers) onto heterogeneous architectures (AMD, Intel, and ARM), significantly increasing the number of possible execution configurations. This flexibility introduces new opportunities for performance and energy optimization.

Instead of running the entire application on a single platform, the decomposition process enables the independent allocation of different functions to distinct hardware, depending on the desired goals—whether optimizing for execution speed, energy consumption, or a balance between the two. In the following sections, we analyze the results obtained from this distribution, examining both the execution time and energy consumption of different configurations.

By comparing the performance across all these configurations, we evaluate how the Decomposer impacts both energy efficiency and execution times, providing insights into potential trade-offs between speed and power usage. The results highlight not only the expanded range of execution scenarios but also the potential for aligning these with specific operational goals, such as meeting SLAs or optimizing for cost and energy savings.

1) *Execution time and energy efficiency:* Decomposer provides enhanced flexibility by enabling the distribution of computational tasks across various hardware configurations

TABLE I: Processing time x energy consumption

	Conv1	Conv2	Conv3	Time (s)	Energy (j)
1	AMD	AMD	AMD	18.174	653.156
2	Intel	AMD	AMD	19.673	635.416
3	AMD	Intel	AMD	21.178	584.611
4	Intel	Intel	AMD	22.677	566.871
5	AMD	AMD	Intel	24.275	479.489
6	AMD	Intel	AMD	25.774	461.749
7	AMD	Intel	Intel	27.279	410.994
8	Intel	Intel	Intel	28.778	393.204
9	ARM	AMD	AMD	28.972	600.440
10	ARM	Intel	AMD	31.976	531.895
11	ARM	AMD	Intel	35.073	426.773
12	ARM	Intel	Intel	38.077	358.228
13	AMD	ARM	AMD	39.824	557.224
14	Intel	ARM	AMD	41.323	539.504
15	AMD	ARM	Intel	45.925	383.577
16	Intel	ARM	Intel	47.424	365.837
17	ARM	ARM	AMD	50.622	504.528
18	ARM	ARM	Intel	56.723	330.861
19	AMD	AMD	ARM	62.116	456.168
20	Intel	AMD	ARM	63.615	438.428
21	AMD	Intel	ARM	65.120	387.623
22	Intel	Intel	ARM	66.619	369.883
23	ARM	AMD	ARM	72.914	403.452
24	ARM	Intel	ARM	75.918	334.907
25	AMD	ARM	ARM	83.766	360.256
26	ARM	Intel	ARM	85.265	342.516
27	ARM	ARM	ARM	94.564	307.540

while maintaining comparable execution times. Table I shows all possible combinations for our 3 decomposed applications (conv1, conv2 and conv3) using 3 different hardware, host 1 (AMD processor), host 2 (ARM processor) and host 4 (Intel processor). As mentioned in Section III-A, the combinations are generated via static analysis, while the data in the time and execution columns were obtained via dynamic analysis, as described in Section III-B. Observe that there are three highlighted rows in the table (rows 1, 8 and 27), where always have the same processor being used in all convolutions. These three rows represent the choices we would have if we used the application in its monolithic form. With Decomposer, all other options are allowed. This approach offers a significant increase in the range of execution strategies, with each configuration presenting unique trade-offs between execution time and energy consumption.

As an example, suppose that a given application accepts a certain processing time of around 40 seconds. In that case, Decomposer would suggest decomposing and deploying the functions using the combination ARM, Intel, Intel (line 12 in Table I), taking 38.07 seconds and consuming 358 joules of energy, which is much less than the best option (line 1), which would consume 653,15 joules of energy.

This work does not intend to analyze which platform performs best overall. The main insight from these results is that Decomposer unlocks the potential to optimize applications for specific operational goals, regardless of the available targets. Depending on whether the priority is performance,

energy efficiency, or a balanced compromise, the application can dynamically assign different functions (e.g., convolution layers) to different hardware platforms. This modular approach allows:

- Performance-critical functions to be executed on faster processors without affecting the overall modular structure.
- Energy-sensitive tasks to be allocated to more efficient hardware, such as ARM, for considerable savings in power consumption.

Thus, Decomposer enables organizations to tailor their execution strategies to meet specific SLAs or KPIs, accommodating both performance demands and energy constraints. What was once a rigid decision between three distinct platforms has now evolved into a broader, more flexible matrix of 27 possible configurations, each offering distinct possibilities for optimization.

Fig. 5: Comparison of execution times (average).

As depicted in Figure 5, the overall execution time analysis reveals minimal differences between the decomposed and monolithic versions. The decomposition process introduces only slight variations in execution time, which are barely noticeable. Even in cases where functions are distributed across a local network or Internet, the impact on execution time remains marginal.

This consistency in performance reinforces the effectiveness of Decomposer in maintaining operational efficiency, while enabling significant flexibility for energy savings and tailored resource allocation without sacrificing speed.

2) *Cache usage impact:* L1 and L2 cache performance results shown in Figure 6 highlight the positive effects of decomposing an application on cache efficiency. L1 misses refer to instances when the processor cannot find the requested data in the L1 cache, causing it to look in the larger and slower L2 cache. L2 references represent these additional memory accesses.

By decomposing the application and distributing workloads across multiple architectures, the number of L1 cache misses decreases, which in turn reduces the need for L2 cache accesses. This improved cache utilization is especially notable on ARM processors, where monolithic execution suffers from substantial L1 misses, leading to higher L2 references. In decomposed configurations, however, both L1 misses and L2 references are significantly reduced, leading to improved cache

Fig. 6: L1 and L2 performance (average).

management and overall performance for all architectures evaluated.

The reduction in L1 misses was 51% for Intel, 68% for AMD and 58% for ARM, when comparing the decomposed over local network (green bar of L1 misses) and monolithic (green bar of L1 misses) strategies. Regarding the reduction in L2 references, comparing the same strategies, a decrease of 52% was observed for Intel, 68% for AMD and 82% for ARM.

The improvement in cache memory utilization can be attributed to the more efficient distribution of workload across multiple cores in the decomposed version of the application. In the monolithic version, the entire application runs on a single core, meaning it only has access to a single L1 cache. As a result, all functions are forced to share the same cache resources, increasing the likelihood of cache misses and forcing more frequent access to higher-level caches or main memory, which are slower.

By contrast, when the application is decomposed, each function can be assigned to a different core. This allows each core to utilize its own dedicated L1 cache, significantly reducing cache contention. The functions no longer compete for the same cache resources, resulting in better cache locality and fewer cache misses. Additionally, this distributed execution reduces the pressure on the memory hierarchy, as each core can manage a smaller working set of data more efficiently. Consequently, the overall system benefits from improved cache performance and reduced memory access latency, which contributes to the better performance observed in the decomposed version of the application.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The Decomposer significantly broadens the possibilities for executing complex applications in heterogeneous environments. By expanding the execution options from 3 to 27 combinations, it highlights that functional decomposition is not only a powerful strategy for improving resource utilization and energy efficiency, but also for enhancing operational flexibility. This expanded flexibility allows for dynamic allocation of workloads based on specific needs, such as high-performance

configurations during peak hours or energy-efficient modes during off-peak periods.

Moreover, Decomposer achieves these benefits without substantial execution time penalties, even when distributing tasks across different hardware architectures. This positions Decomposer as a promising solution for modern IT computing infrastructures (e.g. data centers, edge 5G networks, etc.) where balancing performance, energy consumption, and flexibility is critical to meeting both operational goals and sustainability requirements. By enabling more granular control over execution strategies, businesses can better align their applications with diverse KPIs and SLAs, while optimizing both performance and energy efficiency.

Although this work focuses on convolutional neural networks as a case study, Decomposer is designed to be applicable to a wide range of applications. Future work includes evaluating Decomposer with Polybench, a benchmark suite comprising various numerical kernels frequently used in scientific computing, which will allow us to assess its effectiveness in loop-intensive applications. Additionally, we plan to test Decomposer with the YOLO (You Only Look Once) framework, widely used for real-time object detection, to examine its adaptability in workloads with high computational intensity and data dependency. These evaluations will provide insights into how functional decomposition can be optimized across different computational domains.

In terms of future works, the following items should be pursued:

- One of our main goals for future work is to extend the list of targets to include GPUs, FPGAs and other DPUs.
- In addition, we are working to expand our static analysis to allow integration with data flow graphs (DFGs) and the possibility of subgraph mining.
- We also plan to update Decomposer runtime to allow it to receive as input not only the application, but also KPIs and SLAs related to it, and with these metrics, it can discover and select from the available options the one that will best fit the metrics, facilitating and automating decision making.
- We will also deepen the study related to cache memory improvement.
- Finally, using static analysis we understand that we can determine functions that can or cannot be executed in parallel. As an example, the three convolutions used in this work could be executed in parallel, since there is no data dependency among them. Discovering and executing functions in parallel has the potential to drastically reduce execution time.

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